

A MACHINE LEARNING-BASED QUANTITATIVE STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP STUDY FOR THE ANTICANCER ACTIVITY OF A SERIES OF COMPOUNDS

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Cancer is a collective term used to describe a group of different diseases that are characterized by the loss of control of cell growth and division, leading to a primary tumor that invades and destroys adjacent tissues. It may also spread to other regions of the body through a process known as metastasis, which is the cause of 90% of cancer deaths. Cancer remains one of the most difficult diseases to treat and is responsible for approximately 14.5% of all deaths worldwide. Breast cancer is the most frequent malignancy in females. Due to its major impact on population, this disease represents a critical public health problem that requires further research at the molecular level in order to define its prognosis and specific treatment. Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer and the leading cause of cancer death among females, accounting for 23% of the total cancer cases and 14% of the cancer deaths; thus, research in this field is important to overcome both economical and psychological burden.

Application of machine learning in drug development is one of the most powerful modern directions that help to find the best candidates with anticancer activity. One of these methods called cheminformatics that connects machine learning and chemistry. Cheminformatics (QSAR) is widely applied in pharmaceutical industry predictive and diagnostic process which already helped to discover many drugs currently in the market.

This study is devoted to investigation of 105 compounds applying QSAR analysis to correlate and predict their anticancer activity (AA) to the breast cancer cell line (MCF-7). QSAR analysis was carried out using genetic algorithm (GA) for variables selection and multiple linear regression (MLR) analysis. Quantum-chemical descriptors were calculated and applied as well. The model developed shows not only a statistical significance, but also an excellent predictive ability. The estimated predictive ability (r^2_{test}) of the model for the external set is 0.82 and for the training set is $r^2_{train} = 0.89$, respectively.

Materials and Methods

The dataset for the present study has been collected from several experimental studies [5-7] for a series of 105 compounds with anticancer activity (AA) data. All original activity data has been converted into molar $1/\log(\text{AA})$ response variables.

Results and Discussion

The following equation was selected during the study as a best performing one for AA:

$$\begin{aligned} 1/\text{Log}(\text{AA}) = & 0.001(\pm 0.0005)\text{T}(\text{N..F}) + 6.858(\pm 9.022)\text{X2A} + \\ & 9.937(\pm 3.472)\text{BELm1} + 1.955(\pm 1.510)\text{BELv3} + 0.029(\pm 0.018)\text{RDF080m} + \\ & 0.264(\pm 0.211)\text{Mor18u} - 0.343(\pm 0.211)\text{Mor21u} - 0.030(\pm 0.097)\text{Mor07m} - \\ & 0.155(\pm 0.055)\text{Mor09m} + 21.201(\pm 18.218)\text{G2e} - 10.253(\pm 7.711)\text{ISH} - 3.915(\pm 2.455)\text{HATS3m} - \\ & 57.537(\pm 31.154)\text{R7u} + -3.630(\pm 1.665)\text{R1e} - 0.081(\pm 0.054)\text{n=CR2} - \\ & 0.099(\pm 0.126)\text{nCOOR} + 0.087(\pm 0.261)\text{nNHR} - 8.969(\pm 12.499) \end{aligned}$$

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